

An Attention-Based CNN Approach to Detect Forest Tree Dieback Caused by Insect Outbreak in Sentinel-2 Images

Vito Recchia¹ ,
Gianpietro Fontana¹, and Donato Malerba^{1,2}

¹ Department of Computer Science, University of Bari “Aldo Moro”, Bari, Italy
{vito.recchia, giuseppina.andresini, annalisa.appice,
g.fontana10}@studenti.uniba.it, donato.malerba@uniba.it

² CINI - Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per l'Informatica, Bari, Italy

Abstract. Forests play a key role in maintaining the balance of ecosystems, regulating climate, conserving biodiversity, and supporting various ecological processes. However, insect outbreaks, particularly bark beetle outbreaks, pose a significant threat to European spruce forest health by causing an increase in forest tree mortality. Therefore, developing accurate forest disturbance inventory strategies is crucial to quantifying and promptly mitigating outbreak diseases and boosting effective environmental management. In this paper, we propose a deep learning-based approach, named AVALON, that implements a CNN to detect tree dieback events in Sentinel-2 images of forest areas. To this aim, each pixel of a Sentinel-2 image is transformed into an imagery representation that sees the pixel within its surrounding pixel neighbourhood. We incorporate an attention mechanism into the CNN architecture to gain accuracy and achieve useful insights from the explanations of the spatial arrangement of model decisions. We assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach in two case studies regarding forest scenes in the Northeast of France and the Czech Republic, which were monitored using Sentinel-2 satellite in October 2018 and September 2020, respectively. Both case studies host bark beetle outbreaks in the considered periods.

Keywords: CNNs · Attention · XAI · Remote Sensing · Forest tree dieback · Bark beetle outbreak inventory

1 Introduction

Forest tree dieback refers to the phenomenon of a stand of trees losing health and dying due to pathogens, parasites or conditions like acid rain, drought, wind storm or fire. Nowadays, bark beetle outbreaks represent one of the major causes of tree dieback in European spruce forests. These are small insects that reproduce beneath the bark of coniferous trees, depositing their eggs under the bark and swarming when the temperature is higher. Since 2018, Europe has experienced

© The Author(s) 2025

D. Pedreschi et al. (Eds.): DS 2024, LNAI 15244, pp. 183–199, 2025.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-78980-9_12

several unprecedented bark beetle outbreaks that are repeatedly ruining vast swathes of conifer forests. The accurate inventory of bark beetle outbreaks has a crucial role in quantifying and promptly mitigating the consequences of bark beetle outbreaks and enables forest managers to perform informed tree sanitation cuts. At present, the bark beetle outbreak inventory is commonly performed in Europe by foresters during laborious, time-consuming and expensive field surveys [7]. However, the increasing amount of Sentinel-2 images acquired within the European Space Agency program of Sentinel-2 missions offers today the opportunity to systematically reduce the amount of forestry fieldwork. Sentinel-2 are high-resolution, multi-spectral satellite images, which are acquired with thirteen spectral bands for the Earth observation. They are recorded every five days with a constellation of two identical satellites in the same orbit. The Copernicus Open Access Hub provides complete, free and open access to Sentinel-2 images. Hence, AI methods used to detect bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest areas can allow foresters to scale-up and speed-up the assessment and surveillance of tree dieback caused by bark beetle over large forest areas.

The present study is boosted from amazing results recently achieved with deep learning methods in semantic segmentation of satellite images. The goal of semantic segmentation is to take images and identify imagery patches belonging to specific semantic labels. Bark beetle outbreaks commonly expand into the forests for several tens of meters due to swarming events. Therefore, neighbour information is useful for correctly delineating bark beetle outbreak areas. This makes semantic segmentation approaches appropriate for mapping tree dieback caused by bark beetles. Semantic segmentation is done by processing the image through a deep neural network that performs deep feature extraction and produces a map with a semantic label per pixel. CNNs are among the most widely used deep neural architectures for image analysis due to their ability of leveraging spatial correlation [6] surrounding pixel data during the deep feature extraction. Accordingly, a few studies [17, 20] have recently shown that CNN-based semantic segmentation models can achieve a valuable accuracy performance in mapping bark beetle outbreaks in several types of satellite images included Sentinel-2 images. However, CNNs learn opaque models implicitly represented in the form of a huge number of numerical weights, which are difficult to explain due to the complexity of the network structure. Although, the priority of foresters is to count on accurate semantic labels in satellite images of forest areas, easier-to-explain models are also desirable to better develop a symbiotic AI approach that can better gain trust of foresters in semantic segmentation outputs.

The explainability of semantic segmentation models refers partially to how easily humans may comprehend their underlying assumptions and reasoning. For example, the authors of [2, 5] use XAI to strengthen the results of bark beetle outbreak mapping by explaining the effect of spectral bands on semantic segmentation decisions. These studies explain post-hoc decisions produced with different machine learning methods (i.e., XGBoost, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine) and draw conclusions that are in line with well known achievements already reported in [1] on which spectral bands are affected from

bark beetle outbreaks. Hence, as these explanations show that known spectral patterns underline machine learning reasoning, they allow foresters to gain confidence in approving machine learning decisions. However, they neither contribute to gain accuracy in the semantic segmentation model nor disclose new interpretable knowledge that can facilitate the identification of errors in the semantic segmentation maps.

In this paper, we present a semantic segmentation approach, named AVALON (Attention-based conVolutional neurAL network fOrest tree dieback in seNtinel-2 images), that trains a CNN model for the semantic segmentation of Sentinel-2 images of forest areas. It integrates a pixel attention mechanism [19] that allows the adaptive selection of imagery pixels where the network “sees” the most important spectral information for the local decisions. This mechanism can mitigate local disturbances introduced with useless or noise data (especially along the boundary between patches labelled with opposite semantic labels). On the other hand, the analysis of the results of the attention provides insight into how the CNN model achieves its decisions, by contributing to the enhancement of the explainability of how a pixel neighbourhood contributes to the decision on each semantic label. The experimentation conducted in two case studies, regarding bark beetle outbreaks localised in the Northeast of France in October 2018 and in the Czech Republic in September 2020, show that the attention mechanism allows us to gain semantic segmentation accuracy and provides some overall explanation of the spatial arrangement of decisions. As an additional contribution, we compute the cumulative attention values obtained pixel-wise in every scene to provide a picture of how each pixel contributes to the overall segmentation of the scene. A qualitative analysis of these scene explanation maps shows that these explanations may also help foresters in identifying wrong decisions that may require their fieldwork to be corrected.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces relevant related works. Section 3 describes the proposed approach, while Sect. 4 reports the experimental evaluation and discusses the related findings. Finally, Sect. 5 concludes.

2 Related Works

The remote sensing literature has recently explored the performance of several machine learning and deep learning methods for processing Sentinel-2 images and mapping forest tree dieback caused by bark beetle outbreaks. Most of these studies use machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest [2, 5, 7, 9, 14], Support Vector Machine [5, 9, 10] and XGBoost [2, 5] combined with spectral vegetation indices extracted with different combination of spectral bands.

On the other hand, deep learning strategies have recently seen a massive rise in popularity in several problems of forest health monitoring. For example, the authors of [5] evaluate the performance of deep learning algorithms such as U-Net and FCN-8 as a contribution of their evaluation study. The authors of both [17, 20] analyse the performance of CNN models trained for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in several types of satellite images, including Sentinel-2 images.

However, none of the tested CNN architectures uses the attention mechanism. On the other hand, in [15] the attention mechanism is integrated in a standard U-Net model and uses the defined architecture for detecting deforestation within 3-band and 4-band Sentinel-2 images. In [18], the performance of a U-Net model equipped with the attention mechanism and trained to detect the forest damage induced by bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images is evaluated.

Finally, a few recent studies have started the exploration of the explainability of semantic segmentation models trained for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. In particular, the authors of [5] use SHAP to show that the effect of the spectral input on the decisions yielded by the same model may change according to the classes and, in some cases, according to the machine learning algorithm. In [2], SHAP is used to explain the effect of both temporal spectral data and temporal spectral vegetation indices on decisions yielded from a Random Forest model for bark beetle outbreak mapping. The studies in [15, 18] use the attention mechanism with U-Net models trained for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. However, both these studies neglect the explanation results of attention that is one of the contributions of this study. On the other hand, the work in [16] describes a CNN equipped with attention especially designed for water body extraction from Sentinel-2 images. But, again, the study does not consider explanation information embedded in the attention mechanism. Finally, the authors of [13] have recently explored the use of the attention mechanism in CNNs trained for the scene classification of colour images. Similarly to our work, this study explores achievements of attention in terms of both accuracy and explainability. However, scene classification is a different task where a label is assigned to an entire image, while semantic segmentation is a task where a label is assigned to each imagery pixel.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that couples the evaluation of how an attention mechanism can allow a CNN model to gain accuracy in the inventory of bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images (by outperforming several related machine learning and deep learning models) to the analysis of how explanation insights disclosed with attention can help in gaining trust of foresters in obtained maps also thanks to the identification of symptoms of potential errors in the predicted semantic segmentation maps.

3 Proposed Method

AVALON takes \mathcal{S} – a collection of labelled Sentinel-2 images – as input. Each Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S} is a tensor with shape $W_{\mathbf{S}} \times H_{\mathbf{S}} \times C$, which covers an Earth scene spanned across $W_{\mathbf{S}} \times H_{\mathbf{S}}$ pixels that are observed across C spectral bands. Let $\mathbf{S}(i, j)$ denote the spectral vector with size C recorded at pixel (i, j) in \mathbf{S} . In \mathcal{S} , every Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S} is one-to-one associated with a label mask \mathbf{M} with shape $W_{\mathbf{S}} \times H_{\mathbf{S}}$ so that every $\mathbf{S}(i, j)$ is assigned to a binary semantic label $\mathbf{M}(i, j)$. In this study, each semantic label assumes the value: “healthy” (0) or “damaged” (1). AVALON learns a semantic segmentation model that predict the unknown label mask of any new Sentinel-2 image. This is done by reformulating and addressing

Fig. 1. Schema of AVALON. Abbreviations: FC = Fully Connected

the semantic segmentation problem as an image classification problem. To this aim, we first transform every Sentinel-2 imagery pixel of the input collection into an image that shows the pixel within its pixel neighbourhood. Then, we train a CNN with Attention to image classification. The pipeline of AVALON is shown in Fig. 1.

To achieve a formulation of the semantic segmentation problem as an image classification problem, we transform \mathcal{S} into a new imagery dataset \mathcal{P} . Formally, given a target pixel (i, j) recorded into a Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S} , this is mapped into a pixel image $\mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})}$ with shape $W \times H \times C$, which shows (i, j) within its squared pixel neighbourhood in \mathbf{S} . Let us consider $H = W = 2k + 1$ with k as a user-defined, positive, integer parameter to define the neighbourhood size. $\mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})}$ covers $(2k + 1)^2$ pixels of \mathbf{S} spanned across a pixel neighbourhood $N(i, j, k)$ defined as $N(i, j, k) = \{(i', j') | i - k \leq i' \leq i + k, j - k \leq j' \leq j + k\}$. In the case of boundary pixels, we add padding pixels populated with the average spectral values calculated on the remaining neighbour pixels for each spectral band. Every image $\mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})} \in \mathcal{P}$ is associated with a binary label (0 or 1) that is the label $\mathbf{M}(i, j)$. A CNN model is trained from \mathcal{P} to learn a function to image classification. The used CNN integrates a pixel attention mechanism, as described in [19]. This generates a pixel-wise attention map for all pixels in the input data images. In particular, the pixel attention layer takes as input each tensor \mathbf{X}^l of a given convolutional l -th layer with dimension $W^l \times H^l \times C^l$. It convolves a 1×1 convolution layer followed by a sigmoid function. This is to obtain the attention maps of the level $l + 1$ that are then multiplied with the input pixels at l -th layer. Formally, the pixel attention layer is defined as:

$$\mathbf{X}^{l+1} = \sigma(f(\mathbf{X}^l)) \odot \mathbf{X}^l, \tag{1}$$

where $f()$ is a 1×1 convolution layer, σ is the sigmoid function and \mathbf{X}^{l+1} is the resulting output tensor at $l + 1$ -th layer. The output of this operation is a new tensor \mathbf{X}^{l+1} with shape $W^{l+1} \times H^{l+1} \times C^{l+1}$ where $W^l = W^{l+1}$, $H^l = H^{l+1}$ and $C^l = C^{l+1}$. To produce a single attention map that explains the importance of pixels in the original image, we apply an average layer, as implemented in [3]. This averages all the channels for each corresponding pixel. More in detail, given the tensor with shape $W^{l+1} \times H^{l+1} \times C^{l+1}$ produced by the pixel attention layer,

the average layer produces a single-channel tensor with shape $W^{l+1} \times H^{l+1} \times 1$, for which each attention pixel α_{ij}^{l+1} is equal to:

$$\alpha_{ij}^{l+1} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c=1, \dots, C} \alpha_{ijc}^l, \quad (2)$$

where α_{ijc}^l is the attention pixel at position (i, j) in the c -th feature map from the preceding $l - 1$ layer. The average layer explains visually which pixels of the input image received more attention from the model for the image classification.

The prediction is done by minimizing a binary cross-entropy loss function:

$$\mathcal{H} = -(y \log \hat{y} + (1 - y) \log (1 - \hat{y})), \quad (3)$$

where $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground truth label and \hat{y} is the CNN output for a single pixel image.

4 Evaluation Study

This evaluation study aims at examining the accuracy performance and the explanation insights achieved with AVALON. Section 4.1 describes the case studies considered in the evaluation study and the adopted experimental set-up. Section 4.2 describes the implementation of AVALON. Finally, Sect. 4.3 illustrates the analysis of the accuracy and explainability results achieved in the evaluation.

4.1 Case Studies and Experimental Set-up

We considered two case studies that involve non-overlapping forest scenes spanned across Northeast of France and Czech Republic. The scene collections hosted bark beetle outbreaks. The case study in Northeast of France included 87 forest scenes that hosted bark beetle outbreaks that were likely caused by the hot summer droughts in 2018. The ground truth map of these outbreaks was commissioned by the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food to Sertit (University of Strasbourg), to assess the damage observed in October 2018 in spruce forests of Northeast of France [2, 5]. The case study in Czech Republic included 200 forest scenes that hosted bark beetle outbreaks that were likely caused by the hot summer droughts in 2020. The ground truth map of these outbreaks was acquired in September 2020 and recorded in DEFID2 database [12].

Accordingly, cloud-free Sentinel-2 images were downloaded in October 2018 for the scenes of Northeast of France and in September 2020 for the scenes of Czech Republic, respectively. The images were downloaded in the 3857 EPSG system from the ESA Copernicus open access hub using the Google Earth Engine APIs. Sentinel-2 spectral bands with different spatial resolutions from 10 m were all re-sampled at the same pixel size of 10 m resolution. In the dataset of Northeast of France, the size of the Sentinel-2 images varies from 23×39 to 461×425 pixels at 10m^2 resolution, while the percentage of infested territory per scene

Fig. 2. Location of the centroids of the study 87 scenes in the Northeast of France area (Fig. 2a), and 200 scenes in the Czech Republic (Fig. 2b). The red circles are the training set scenes, while the blue circles are the testing set scenes. (Color figure online)

varies from 0,33% to 34,8% of the scene surface. The total percentage of damaged territory of the entire scene collection is 2,81%. The semantic segmentation model development and its evaluation were conducted by considering 71 random scenes (covering 1639945 pixels at 10 m^2 resolution) as training scene set and 16 left-out scenes (covering 495223 pixels) as testing scene set. In the dataset of Czech Republic, the size of images varies from 33×36 to 260×238 pixels at 10 m^2 resolution, while the percentage of infested territory per scene varies from 4,14% to 54,81% of the scene surface. The total percentage of damaged territory of the entire scene collection is 14,59%. The semantic segmentation model development and its evaluation were conducted by considering 160 random scenes (covering 1014708 pixels at 10 m^2 resolution) as training scene set and 40 left-out scenes (covering 198253 pixels) as testing scene set. Figures 2a and 2b show the maps of the location of study scenes in Northeast of France and Czech Republic, as well as the partitioning of each scene set in the training scene set and testing scene set.

4.2 Implementation Details

AVALON was developed in Python 3.¹ In particular, the CNN architecture was implemented using the PyTorch library (version 2.0.1). For each dataset, we conducted a Bayesian optimization of the CNN hyperparameters with the tree-structured Parzen estimator algorithm, as implemented in the Optuna library. Specifically, we optimized the set-up of the following hyperparameters: mini-batch size in $\{2^5, 2^6, 2^7, 2^8\}$, learning rate between 0.0001 and 0.001, number of kernel size in $\{2, 3, 4\}$, number of Convolutional layers in $\{1, 2, 3\}$ and dropout between 0 and 1. The hyperparameter optimisation was performed using 20% of the entire training set (selected with stratified sampling) as a validation set. We selected the configuration of hyperparameters that achieved the highest F1

¹ Code and parameters of trained model available at <https://github.com/s4rgax/AVALON>.

computed on the validation set by considering the class “damaged” as the positive class. The CNN architecture was defined with a variable number of Convolutional layers, a Pixel Attention layer placed after the last Convolutional layer in the neural network, and two Fully-Connected layers. A Dropout layer was placed between each pair of Convolutional layers to perform data regularisation and prevent training data overfitting. In all layers, except the final classification layer, the Rectified Linear Unit function (ReLU) was used as the activation function. The Softmax activation function was used in the classification layer. We performed the gradient-based optimisation using the Adam update rule. Finally, we trained the CNN model with the maximum number of epochs set equal to 150, and using an early-stopping approach to retain the best model.

4.3 Result and Discussion

In this Section we illustrated the results achieved in: (1) the study of the sensitivity of the accuracy performance of AVALON to the size of pixel neighbourhoods considered, as well as the ablation study to explore the effect of the attention mechanism on the accuracy performance of the proposed method; (2) the comparative analysis of the accuracy performance of related methods commonly used in the remote sensing literature on bark beetle detection; and (3) the qualitative analysis of the explanations produced with the attention mechanism in AVALON.

Accuracy Performance Analysis. To evaluate the accuracy performance we measured the following metrics: F1 score (F1) computed for the two opposite semantic labels, Macro F1 score (Macro F1) averaged on the two labels and Intersection-over-Union (IoU). The F1 score measures the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall. The Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ is the fraction of pixels correctly classified in a specific class (TP) among pixels of the considered class ($TP+FP$). The Recall = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ is the fraction of pixels correctly classified in a specific class (TP) among pixels classified in the considered class ($TP+FN$). The IoU score is the ratio of the intersected area to the combined area of prediction and ground truth, that is, $\text{IoU} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP+FN}$. This is commonly used to evaluate the accuracy of models trained in both semantic segmentation and object detection problems. All metrics are reported in percentages and computed on the Sentinel-2 images collected for the testing scenes. For each metric, the higher the value, the better the performance of the semantic segmentation maps predicted.

Table 1 reports the accuracy performance of AVALON in the two case studies by varying the size of each squared pixel neighbourhood among 3×3 , 5×5 and 7×7 . This sensitivity analysis of the effect of the neighbourhood size on the accuracy performance of AVALON was performed orthogonal to an ablation study that compared the performance of the AVALON models trained with the attention mechanism to the performance of the AVALON models trained by keeping away the attention mechanism. The results show that each configuration of AVALON run with the attention outperforms the counterpart configuration run without the attention independently of the pixel neighbourhood size. On the other hand, in both case studies, the best accuracy performance is achieved with

Table 1. Accuracy performance of semantic segmentation maps produced with the configurations of AVALON obtained by varying the size of each pixel neighbourhood among 3×3 , 5×5 and 7×7 , considering the attention mechanism, as well as neglecting it, in the two case studies in Northeast of France and Czech Republic, respectively. The best results are in bold.

AVALON configuration		Northeast of France				Czech Republic			
Neighb.	Attention	F1(d)	F1(h)	Macro F1	IoU	F1(d)	F1(h)	Macro F1	IoU
3×3	No	59.60	99.35	79.47	42.45	65.09	92.94	79.02	48.25
5×5	No	66.12	99.39	82.76	49.39	67.76	93.70	80.73	51.24
7×7	No	63.80	99.40	81.60	46.84	66.86	93.09	79.97	50.21
3×3	Yes	65.75	99.41	82.58	48.97	69.00	93.73	81.37	52.68
5×5	Yes	68.90	99.45	84.18	52.56	70.73	93.64	82.19	54.72
7×7	Yes	68.45	99.44	83.94	52.03	69.15	93.86	81.51	52.85

Fig. 3. Box plots of F1(d) scores computed per scene with AVALON in the testing Sentinel-2 images of Northeast of France and Czech Republic, respectively

pixel neighbourhoods with size 5×5 . By considering that a pixel covers 10 m^2 , this analysis shows that, independently of the case study, a local area of 50 m^2 is a reasonable choice to account for the spatial correlation of spectral bands in bark beetle outbreak mapping. The only exception was observed in the F1(h), that is, the F1 score computed on the majority class “healthy”, in the case study in Czech Republic. In this case, the highest F1(h) was achieved in the configuration of AVALON run with the pixel neighbourhood size set equal to 7×7 , while the highest F1(d), as well as the highest Macro F1 and IoU, were still achieved in the configuration of AVALON with the pixel neighbourhood size set equal to 5×5 . Foresters are, in general, more interested in better delineating bark beetle outbreak areas than healthy areas. So, the improvement in F1(d) is more desirable than the improvement in F1(h). Hence, we consider the configuration of AVALON using the attention mechanism and processing pixel neighbourhoods with a size set equal to 5×5 in the follow-up of this evaluation study.

Figure 3 shows the box plots of F1(d) scores computed with AVALON, scene by scene, in the testing Sentinel-2 images of Northeast of France and Czech Republic. Although the F1(d) score is higher, on average, in Northeast of France than in Czech Republic, we note higher variability of F1(d) in Czech Republic with a few close-to-zero outliers. In the subsequent explanation analysis, we

show that explanation maps extracted with AVALON may help foresters to identify signals of potentially inaccurate predictions in these semantic segmentation maps.

Competitor Analysis. We compare the accuracy performance of AVALON to that of machine learning and deep learning methods (i.e., Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, Multi-Layer Perceptron, YOLO8-Seg, U-Net and Attention U-Net) commonly used in literature studies on bark beetle outbreak detection in Sentinel-2 data. As described in [5], a grid search was used to optimise the selection of the label cost in Random Forest, XGBoost and Support Vector Machine, as well as the tree depth in Random Forest and XGBoost. The Multi-Layer Perceptron was composed of a number of fully connected layers varying between 3 and 6. The number of neurons per layer was a power of two, with the final layer having 32 neurons, and the output probabilities were obtained using the softmax activation function. The ReLU activation function was used in all the other hidden layers. The number of layers was selected by maximising the F1 score computed on the class “damaged” for a validation set (20% of the training set). The YOLO8-Seg architecture consists of a revised version of the object detector YOLO (You Only Look Once) for segmentation tasks. In particular, for this experimental evaluation, we fine-tuned the version 8 of YOLO model released in January 2023 by Ultralytics² with the RGB images of the two case studies considered in this paper. The U-Net architecture included an encoder repeating blocks with a 3×3 convolutional layer with a spatial Dropout, a Batch Normalization layer and a 2×2 Max Pooling operation layer. At each downsampling step of the encoder, the number of feature channels was increased. In the decoder, the feature map was upsampled through a sequence of up-convolutions that halved the number of feature channels and concatenated the result with the features from the corresponding encoder layer. The classification of each pixel map was obtained by using the Sigmoid activation function. The ReLU was used in all hidden convolution layers. The Tversky loss was used to handle the data imbalance. Finally, the Attention U-Net was implemented by integrating the pixel attention within the skip connections between the downsampling path and the upsampling path of the U-Net.

Table 2 reports the accuracy performance of the compared methods in the two case studies. AVALON achieves the best performance in all the accuracy metrics measured in this evaluation study in both Northeast of France and Czech Republic. The Attention U-Net is the runner-up of this comparative study. Notably, the Attention U-Net uses the same pixel attention module embedded in AVALON, but within the encoder-decoder architecture of a U-Net model, while AVALON integrates pixel attention in a CNN architecture. So, these results show that the attention mechanism can actually help us to better map bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. In addition, the attention-based approach developed in AVALON outperforms the Attention U-Net showing that better accuracy performance can be achieved in the considered task using a CNN architecture.

² <https://docs.ultralytics.com/it/tasks/segment/>.

Table 2. Accuracy performance of semantic segmentation maps produced with both AVALON and related methods in Northeast of France and Czech Republic, respectively. The best results are in bold.

Method	Northeast of France				Czech Republic			
	F1(d)	F1(h)	Macro F1	IoU	F1(d)	F1(h)	Macro F1	IoU
Random Forest	61.35	99.32	80.34	44.25	67.43	92.76	80.09	50.86
XGBoost	59.54	99.25	79.39	42.39	67.10	92.20	79.65	50.49
Support Vector Machine	60.38	99.19	79.79	43.25	68.59	92.33	80.46	52.20
Multi-Layer Perceptron	54.89	99.01	76.95	37.82	65.97	92.26	79.12	49.22
YOLO8-Seg	47.07	98.98	73.02	30.78	61.27	90.90	76.09	44.17
U-Net	63.18	99.38	81.28	46.18	67.58	90.78	79.18	51.03
Attention U-Net	65.68	99.29	82.48	48.90	68.65	91.41	80.03	52.27
AVALON	68.90	99.45	84.18	52.56	70.73	93.64	82.19	54.72

Fig. 4. Critical difference diagram of Friedman-Nemenyi test performed on F1(d) measured on the semantics segmentation maps of evaluated scenes produced with Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), YOLO8-Seg, U-Net, Attention U-Net, and AVALON in Northeast of France (Fig. 4a) and Czech Republic (Fig. 4b)

Figures 4a and 4b report the Friedman-Nemenyi test of the F1(d) scores measured for both AVALON and the related methods on the testing scenes in both Northeast of France and Czech Republic. The results of this comparative test support the conclusion that AVALON generally achieves higher F1(d), measured on the testing scenes, than the related methods.

Explainability Analysis. Finally, we perform a qualitative analysis of explanations produced with the pixel attention mechanism integrated in AVALON. We recall that AVALON addresses a semantic segmentation task as an image classification problem by mapping each Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S} of a forest scene into a collection of pixel neighbourhood-based images. It assigns a semantic label to each imagery scene pixel by assigning a class label to each associated image of the pixel neighbourhood. Accordingly, AVALON produces the attention maps of the neighbourhood-based images of the scene pixels to explain the decisions produced for the scene pixels accounting for the information enclosed in their neighbour pixels. Specifically, for each pixel (i, j) in \mathbf{S} , the pixel attention map

Algorithm 1: Attention Scene Map of a Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S}

Data: A Sentinel-2 image \mathbf{S} with shape $W_{\mathbf{S}} \times H_{\mathbf{S}} \times C$; the Attention-CNN model; the neighbourhood size parameter k

Result: The attention map \mathbf{A} computed for \mathbf{S} with shape $W_{\mathbf{S}} \times H_{\mathbf{S}}$

```

1 begin
2    $\mathbf{A} = \text{zeros}(W_{\mathbf{S}}, H_{\mathbf{S}})$ 
3    $\text{Counter} = \text{zeros}(W_{\mathbf{S}}, H_{\mathbf{S}})$ 
4   for  $(i = 1; i \leq W_{\mathbf{S}}; i++)$  do
5     for  $(j = 1; j \leq H_{\mathbf{S}}; j++)$  do
6        $\hat{y}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})} = \text{predict}(\text{CNN}, \mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})})$ 
7        $\mathbf{a}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})} = \text{attentionMap}(\text{CNN}, \mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})})$ 
8       if  $\hat{y}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})} == 1$  then
9          $\mathbf{A}[i - k : i + k, j - k : j + k] += a_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})}$ 
10        else
11           $\mathbf{A}[i - k : i + k, j - k : j + k] += -1 \cdot a_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})}$ 
12           $\text{Counter} = [i - k : i + k, j - k : j + k] += 1$ 
13    $\mathbf{A} = \text{minmaxScaler}(\mathbf{A} / \text{Counter})$ 
14   return  $\mathbf{A}$ 

```

Fig. 5. RGB images, Ground truth (GT) label masks, Predicted semantic segmentation masks (Pred) and Scene Attention maps (A) of two scenes in Northeast of France. Figures 5a–d refer to a scene for which AVALON achieved $F(d) = 0.87$. Figures 5e–h refer to a scene for which AVALON achieved $F(d) = 0.49$. (Color figure online)

of the pixel neighbourhood-based image $\mathbf{P}_{(i,j,\mathbf{S})}$ sees which pixels in the considered neighbourhood received more attention from the CNN model to predict the semantic label of (i, j) . Based on these premises, we combined all pixel attention maps produced in a scene, as described in Algorithm 1, to yield the overall attention map of a Sentinel-2 imagery scene. In particular, for each pixel in \mathbf{S} , we sum up the attention values that are computed for the pixel in every neighbourhood-based image extracted from \mathbf{S} where the pixel appears as a target pixel or neighbour pixel. Notice that each attention value is a positive, real value. To distinguish between pixels that are seen to predict “healthy” labels and pixels that are seen to predict “damaged” labels, attention values of pixels are multiplied by -1 when they are part of a pixel-neighbourhood image predicted in the class “healthy”, while they are considered in their original positive format when they are part of a pixel-based neighbourhood image predicted in the class “damaged”. Finally, every accumulated pixel attention value is averaged with respect to the number of single attention values accumulated for the pixel in the scene and scaled between 0 and 1 to be visualised in a heatmap.

Figures 5 and 6 show the RGB bands, ground truth label masks, predicted semantic segmentation masks and scene attention maps of two Sentinel-2 images selected from the testing sets of Northeast of France and Czech Republic,

Fig. 6. RGB images, Ground truth label masks (GT), Predicted semantic segmentation masks (Pred) and Scene Attention maps (A) of two scenes in Czech Republic. Figures 6a–d refer to a scene for which AVALON achieved $F1(d) = 0.71$. Figures 6e–h refer to a scene where AVALON achieved $F1(d) = 0.04$. (Color figure online)

respectively. In both case studies, the two scenes were selected as scenes where AVALON achieved high $F1(d)$ (i.e., $F1(d) = 0.87$ and $F1(d) = 0.71$ in Figs. 5c and 6c) and low $F1(d)$ (i.e., $F1(d) = 0.49$ and $F1(d) = 0.04$ in Figs. 5g and 6g), respectively. The scene attention maps plotted in Figs. 5d and 6d show that the zones that received higher attention delimit well the patches where AVALON predicted the presence of a bark beetle outbreaks in Figs. 5c and 6c, respectively. We recall that AVALON achieved high $F1(d)$ in both these scenes, so this type of explanation outcomes can be used as a visual explanation for foresters of the certainty of the predictions produced for these scenes. On the other hand, the scene attention maps plotted in Figs. 5h and 6h show signals of low certainty for predictions produced from AVALON in these two scenes and plotted in Figs. 5g and 6g. We recall that AVALON achieved low accuracy performance in both these scenes, so this scene explanation outcome can be seen as an alert for foresters who may decide to integrate inventory results of AVALON in critical zones with the inventory produced with traditional fieldwork.

In particular, the predicted mask plotted in Fig. 5g shows a small patch wrongly detected as “damaged” in the bottom-right of the scene. However, the attention map of this scene reported in Fig. 5h shows that AVALON devoted little attention to seeing a bark beetle outbreak in this patch. Differently, the patch correctly predicted in the same scene is highlighted with high attention values in the corresponding scene attention map. Similarly, the predicted mask plotted in Fig. 6g shows that AVALON fails in delimiting outbreak zones in the centre-up of the scene. However, the attention map of the scene reported in Fig. 6h shows some uncertainty in this area. In fact, attention values take on a light shade of blue in the missed outbreak patches (wrongly detected as “healthy”), which is in contrast to the dark shade of blue we observe in the attention value of patches correctly labelled as “healthy”. Further conclusions can be drawn from the scene attention map shown in Fig. 6d in correspondence with the predicted mask shown in Fig. 6c. In this case, AVALON wrongly labels a patch in the centre-up of the scene as “damaged”, and the attention values of the patch show that AVALON actually pays attention to the zone. However, the red extension of the attention (where, anyway, we note a prevalence of yellow and green) is limited

Fig. 7. Pixel attention map for a “damaged” (D) pixel (Fig. 7a) and a “healthy” (H) pixel (Fig. 7b) selected from the Sentinel-2 image shown in Fig. 6a.

compared to other patches correctly predicted as "damaged" in the same scene. In general, we note that this analysis is coherent with our symbiotic view of AI, where an AI semantic segmentation model explains its decisions so that foresters may have an active role in revising the AI-based decision process to achieve the best inventory outcome in problems of bark beetle outbreak detection.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows the pixel attention maps produced with AVALON for two pixels of opposite classes in the scene of Fig. 6a. Both pixels were selected along the boundary of opposite classes. The plots show that the CNN is able to give more attention to the inner pixels that have the same class as the target one, while it gives less attention to pixels of the opposite class. This outcome supports our idea that the attention mechanism allows the CNN model of AVALON to recognise neighbour pixels of a fixed-size neighbourhood, which presumably belong to the same class of the target pixel and which plausibly provide the more relevant spectral information of the neighbourhood for the decision.

5 Discussions and Conclusions

In this paper, we presented an Attention-CNN architecture trained to perform the inventory of bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest scenes. The accuracy of the proposed method AVALON was evaluated in two case studies, which refer to forest scenes infested by bark beetles in Northeast of France and Czech Republic, respectively. The obtained results show that AVALON outperforms related models trained with machine learning and deep learning methods commonly considered in the literature studies addressing the same task. Furthermore, the qualitative evaluation highlights that attention-based explanations may disclose useful information on the effect of the spatial arrangement of imagery data on predictions. Notably, they may also provide a visual guideline that can help foresters identify potentially incorrect predictions.

Beyond the valuable results achieved by AVALON in terms of accuracy and explanation, several limitations still require further investigations. With this regard, we intend to investigate how the proposed approach can be effectively used to map tree dieback areas caused by different families of insect and fungal pathogens. In addition, we plan to explore how the semantic segmentation

model trained with the proposed approach can be used to detect tree dieback areas in geographic areas different from the geographic areas considered for the model training. With regard to the XAI contribution, we plan to explore how explanation information disclosed with the pixel attention module integrated with AVALON can be confirmed or integrated using an XAI post-hoc explanation approach such as Grad-CAM [8]. In addition, we plan to leverage recent results achieved in the cybersecurity domain [11] to distil attention information for gaining accuracy in problems of bark beetle outbreak detection. Finally, we intend to extend the current research to consider Attention-CNNs trained from time-series of Sentinel-2 images. Based on literature [2, 7], feature extraction to identify temporal spectral changes may facilitate the early detection of bark beetle outbreaks. Notably, this direction is coherent with an emerging remote sensing research trend that is assigning a crucial role to change detection analysis [4] in Sentinel-2 images.

Acknowledgments. Annalisa Appice and Donato Malerba acknowledge support from the SWIFTT project, funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement 101082732. Giuseppina Andresini and Vito Recchia are supported by the project FAIR - Future AI Research (PE00000013), Spoke 6 - Symbiotic AI, under the NRRP MUR program funded by the European Union- NextGenerationEU.

Authorship Contribution Statement

Vito Recchia. Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Software, Validation, Visualization, Investigation, Writing - original draft **Giuseppina Andresini:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Supervision, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing **Annalisa Appice:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Gianpietro Fontana:** Software. **Donato Malerba:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.

References

1. Abdullah, H., Skidmore, A.K., Darvishzadeh, R., Heurich, M.: Sentinel-2 accurately maps green-attack stage of European spruce bark beetle (*ips typographus*, l.) compared with Landsat-8. *Remote Sens. Ecol. Conserv.* **5**(1), 87–106 (2019)
2. Andresini, G., Appice, A., Malerba, D.: Leveraging sentinel-2 time series for bark beetle-induced forest dieback inventory. In: *The 39th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing*. SAC 2024, pp. 875–882. ACM (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3605098.3635908>
3. Andresini, G., Appice, A., Caforio, F.P., Malerba, D., Vessio, G.: ROULETTE: a neural attention multi-output model for explainable network intrusion detection. *Expert Syst. Appl.* 117144 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.117144>
4. Andresini, G., Appice, A., Ienco, D., Malerba, D.: Seneca: change detection in optical imagery using Siamese networks with active-transfer learning. *Expert Syst. Appl.* **214**, 119123 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.119123>

5. Andresini, G., Appice, A., Malerba, D.: SILVIA: an explainable framework to map bark beetle infestation in sentinel-2 images. *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.* **16**, 10050–10066 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2023.3312521>
6. Appice, A., Malerba, D.: Segmentation-aided classification of hyperspectral data using spatial dependency of spectral bands. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote. Sens.* **147**, 215–231 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.11.023>
7. Bárta, V., Lukeš, P., Homolová, L.: Early detection of bark beetle infestation in Norway spruce forests of central Europe using Sentinel-2. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.* **100**, 102335 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2021.102335>
8. Caforio, F.P., Andresini, G., Vessio, G., Appice, A., Malerba, D.: Leveraging grad-CAM to improve the accuracy of network intrusion detection systems. In: Soares, C., Torgo, L. (eds.) *DS 2021. LNCS (LNAI)*, vol. 12986, pp. 385–400. Springer, Cham (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88942-5_30
9. Candotti, A., De Giglio, M., Dubbini, M., Tomelleri, E.: A Sentinel-2 based multi-temporal monitoring framework for wind and bark beetle detection and damage mapping. *Remote Sens.* **14**(23) (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14236105>
10. Dalponte, M., Solano-Correa, Y.T., Frizzera, L., Gianelle, D.: Mapping a European spruce bark beetle outbreak using Sentinel-2 remote sensing data. *Remote Sens.* **14**(13) (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14133135>
11. De Rose, L., Andresini, G., Appice, A., Malerba, D.: Vincent: cyber-threat detection through vision transformers and knowledge distillation. *Comput. Secur.* 103926 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2024.103926>
12. Forzieri, G., Dutrieux, L., et al.: The database of European forest insect and disease disturbances: DEFID2. *Glob. Change Biol.* **29**(21), 6040–6065 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16912>
13. Hou, Y.E., Yang, K., Dang, L., Liu, Y.: Contextual spatial-channel attention network for remote sensing scene classification. *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.* **20**, 1–5 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2023.3304645>
14. Huo, L., Persson, H.J., Lindberg, E.: Early detection of forest stress from European spruce bark beetle attack, and a new vegetation index: normalized distance red & SWIR (NDRS). *Remote Sens. Environ.* **255**, 112240 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112240>
15. John, D., Zhang, C.: An attention-based U-Net for detecting deforestation within satellite sensor imagery. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.* **107**, 102685 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2022.102685>
16. Parajuli, J., Fernandez-Beltran, R., Kang, J., Pla, F.: Attentional dense convolutional neural network for water body extraction from Sentinel-2 images. *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Appl. Earth Observ. Remote Sens.* **15**, 6804–6816 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2022.3198497>
17. Turkulainen, E., Honkavaara, E., Näsi, R., et al.: Comparison of deep neural networks in the classification of bark beetle-induced spruce damage using UAS images. *Remote Sens.* **15**(20) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15204928>
18. Zhang, J., Cong, S., Zhang, G., Ma, Y., Zhang, Y., Huang, J.: Detecting pest-infested forest damage through multispectral satellite imagery and improved UNet++. *Sensors* **22**(19) (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22197440>
19. Zhao, H., Kong, X., He, J., Qiao, Yu., Dong, C.: Efficient image super-resolution using pixel attention. In: Bartoli, A., Fusiello, A. (eds.) *ECCV 2020. LNCS*, vol. 12537, pp. 56–72. Springer, Cham (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-67070-2_3

20. Zwieback, S., Young-Robertson, J., et al.: Low-severity spruce beetle infestation mapped from high-resolution satellite imagery with a convolutional network. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote. Sens.* **212**, 412–421 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2024.05.013>

Open Access This chapter is licensed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license and indicate if changes were made.

The images or other third party material in this chapter are included in the chapter's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the chapter's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder.

